

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Finnish farmers want to promote soil biodiversity through alternative tillage methods

Ploughing has been widely used in Finland to prevent the prolific growth of perennial weeds. Inspired by the research findings, a group of farmers, mostly organic cereal growers, considered the potential of minimum or reduced tillage. The farmers were aware that deep ploughing can damage soil structure, lead to soil compaction and cause problems including soil water management. Farmers were very interested to hear about the effects of tillage on soil biodiversity. Many of them have already tried or would be willing to try minimum tillage or direct seeding. Farmers were told that, according to initial research results, infrequent spring ploughing does not seem to be detrimental to the biological community in the soil where its structure and health have been taken care of. Even after the

third ploughing year, the adverse effects of autumn ploughing on earthworms were still quite moderate. Farmers were interested in experimenting with spring ploughing instead of autumn ploughing in places where spring ploughing is possible at all. However, they were concerned about the availability of the necessary tillage equipment, which could be solved by sharing with other farmers. Farmers also called for more information based on long-term on-farm trials and specifically for research on perennial weed management and the economic impact of alternative methods to ploughing to support their choices. Increased administrative burden and lack of resources (time and money) were seen by farmers as barriers to the adoption of new farming practices.

1. Mouldboard ploughing by tractor

2. Minimum tillage with direct sowing of seeds

3. Wheat field

KEYWORDS

Mouldboard ploughing, minimum tillage, direct seeding, Finnish farmer, cereal crop, soil biodiversity, tillage

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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